

Cybersecurity in Nepal's Banking Sector: Gaps, Global Standards, and Policy Alignment

Technical Report

Krishna Bhattarai
Independent Researcher
Kathmandu, Nepal

2025

Abstract

This report examines the current state of cybersecurity in Nepal, highlighting the gaps between existing policies and international standards. As Nepal increasingly digitalizes sectors like banking, government, and education, a strong cybersecurity framework becomes critical. While frameworks such as the Electronic Transaction Act 2063 and the National Cybersecurity Policy 2023 exist, they do not adequately address emerging threats or sector-specific risks.

This report compares Nepal's policies with global standards, including the NIST Cybersecurity Framework, PCI DSS, and ISO 27001, and includes a case study comparing Nepal's commercial banks with JPMorgan Chase & Co., highlighting areas needing improvement. Practical solutions are suggested, such as developing sector-specific policies, stricter enforcement, leveraging AI for threat detection, and increasing public awareness.

By aligning Nepal's policies with global standards and implementing these measures, Nepal can strengthen its cybersecurity resilience and safeguard critical sectors against evolving digital threats.

Keywords: cybersecurity, Nepal, banking, NIST, ISO 27001, policy, digital security

Table of Contents

Abstract	2
Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	4
List of Abbreviation	5
Chapter 1: Introduction	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Problem statement	2
1.3 Objectives	2
1.4 Rationale	2
Chapter 2: Literature Review	3
2.1 Globally implemented standards	3
2.2 Nepal's cybersecurity policy	4
2.3 Identifying the gap	5
2.4 Analysis and Implications	6
Chapter 3: Methodology	7
3.1 Research Method	7
3.2 Framework Comparison and Analysis	7
3.2.1 Common policies of Frameworks	7
3.2.2 Distinctive policies of Frameworks	8
3.3 Case Study on Cybersecurity Policies: Nepalese vs. International Banks	9
3.4 Recommendations	11
Chapter 4: Conclusion	13
References	14
KrishnaBhattarai	3

List of Tables

Table 1 Global standards for cybersecurity framework

4

List of Abbreviation

1. IT: Information Technology
2. NIST: National Institute of Standards and Technology
3. ISO: International Organization for Standardization
4. PCI DSS: Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard
5. ETA: Electronic Transaction Act
6. PA DSS: Payment Application Data Security Standard
7. TSA: Trust Services Criteria
8. RTS: Regulatory Technical Standards
9. SCA: Strong Customer Authentication
10. VAPT: Vulnerability Assessment and Penetration Testing

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

The field of Information Technology is ever changing and evolving. With everything digitalized, the importance of cybersecurity continues to grow, making it a vital part of our life. Cybersecurity can be defined as the process of safeguarding one's network, system or information from unauthorized access. [1] Globally, many countries have started adopting cybersecurity framework such as the NIST's cybersecurity framework that overlooks the security standards within the USA which emphasizes on identify, protect, detect, respond and recover, ISO 27001 and ISO 27002 which provide a framework for safeguarding data through strong policies and best practices, PCI DSS for secured payment card transactions [2], etc. All these frameworks are widely used in crucial sectors such as banking, health and other infrastructure providing cyber-resilience comprehensive guidelines.

In Nepal, sectors like government, banking, education, etc. have started adopting digital solutions. However, due to lack of proper policies and global standard practices, these sectors remain vulnerable to cyber threats [3]. Although Nepal has been adopting cybersecurity frameworks such as the Electronic Transaction Act 2063 (**section 47** being most used), Nepal's first cyber law, which oversees cyber-related issues, digital transactions framework and penalizes cybercrimes [4] but doesn't cover emerging threats [5] and NTA and **Base III** frameworks for **banking** sector exists. In 2023, Nepal disclosed the National Cybersecurity Policy 2023 but it still isn't up to the global standards [6].

This leaves Nepal unprotected against cyber related issues and crimes particularly as Nepal's financial sectors such as banking are widely adopting digitalized services. Although the revised laws provide certain frameworks and standards, it still isn't enough to create a strong defense system for the evolving threats. For this, adopting globally recognized standards such as NIST CSF or ISO/IEC 27001 could better protect Nepal's critical sector and help create a secured digital environment.

1.2 Problem statement

With rapid digitalization, development of cybersecurity frameworks and standard guidelines is crucial in sectors such as government, ecommerce, education, etc. and more so on the financial sector. Despite the existence of frameworks such as the ETA and National Cybersecurity Policy 2023, Nepal still faces challenges such as outdated standards and policies and insufficient alignment with the global standards along with lack of awareness [7].

This report aims to cover the gap between Nepal's existing cybersecurity frameworks and compare it with global standard frameworks, identify the weakness and the lacking area and suggest an actionable solution to enhance the country's cybersecurity policies.

1.3 Objectives

The following are the objectives of this report:

- To explore global cybersecurity standards and analyse Nepal's financial sector's current cybersecurity policies and identify gaps
- To suggest applicable global standards for policy and risk management which can contribute to Nepal's cybersecurity architecture enhancement.

1.4 Rationale

Cyber-attacks will become more frequent as everything gets more digitalized, jeopardizing crucial industries like banking. Existing frameworks, like the National Cybersecurity Policy 2023 and the Electronic Transaction Act, are in place, but they are out of date and do not target particular industries. By implementing internationally accepted cybersecurity standards, these gaps will be filled, thereby enhancing Nepal's digital security and offering improved defences for its changing digital landscape.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Globally implemented standards

Banking and other financial sectors have become a major attack point for threat actors due to their reliance on digital systems. Cyber attackers attack vulnerabilities on mobile banking, online payment, etc. for financial gain. For such, there are some globally recognized and followed frameworks. Global standards are the frameworks and policies that are implemented globally for addressing vulnerabilities and managing risks. [8] Some of such globally implemented standards are as follows:

Global standard for cybersecurity in financial sectors	Provision
1. NIST Cybersecurity Framework 2.0 (National Institute of Standards and Technology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- NIST is a cybersecurity framework that provides guidelines to different sectors to manage cyber related risks.- The updated version is mainly applicable to the financial sector as it focuses on SaaS and cloud solution technology.- This framework helps manage sensitive data and protect it from cyber-attacks. [9]
2. EU Payment Services Directives 2 (PSD2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The PSD2 is an EU cybersecurity framework that focuses on managing and increasing the security of payment systems and protecting customer data.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This standard ensures Strong Customer Authentication (SCA) and data access control measures.
3. Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard (PCI DSS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PCI DSS is a globally recognized framework that focuses on protecting credit and debit card payment systems. - There are certain obligations that must be addressed and breaches of PCI DSS can lead to fines and penalties and restrictions in using credit cards. [10]
4. System and Organization Controls (SOC2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SOC2 is used as a framework to ensure data management and focuses on 5 principles of cybersecurity: security, availability, integrity, confidentiality and privacy. - Helps financial sectors to protect the information of their customers and also third party vendors' security standards are strictly followed. [11]

Table 1 Global standards for cybersecurity framework

2.2 Nepal's cybersecurity policy

Nepal has a limited cybersecurity framework that guides Nepal's digital architecture and lacks any sector specific cybersecurity policies. [12] Although Nepal has certain cybersecurity frameworks such as the Electronic Transaction Act 2063 that mentions cybercrimes and punishments for the same such as: Unauthorized access in computer materials will result to up to 3 years in prison or NPR 2 lakhs or both, divulsion of

confidentiality will result to up to 2 years in prison or 1 lakh fine or both, etc. [13] It doesn't really cover sector specific risks and the framework standards isn't up to date with the advancing threats. [14]

The recently developed National Cybersecurity Policy 2023 is Nepal's current response to tackle the evolving cyber threats. The policy aims to narrow down the gap that exists in Nepal's cyber laws. The framework highlights are data protection and privacy, incident response and research and development by aligning them with global standards.

In the financial sector, the Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB) has released guidelines as cybersecurity resilience frameworks that are to be implemented by all banks. The policies include creating robust standards for cyber related threats, risk appetite, direct involvement of senior management and BOD, identification and assessment of important assets and update policies to get enhanced security. [15]

2.3 Identifying the gap

The gap is visible in Nepal's cybersecurity policies when being compared to global standards. It can be observed that Global standard policies have well-defined sector-specific policies that focus on customer authentication, third party security standards and well developed technology such as SaaS and cloud technology. Although there are existing frameworks that deal with cyber related issues in Nepal, they are not really up to the standards and not sector specific policies. There are fines and penalties implemented but they are not enforceable enough to solve the emerging cybersecurity challenges. [16]

2.4 Analysis and Implications

In my perspective, Nepal has a foundation level cybersecurity policies but they don't really address the emerging threats. For this, the current cybersecurity policies should be improvised and applicable global standards should be implemented. As mentioned earlier, Nepal lacks sector-specific cybersecurity policies which makes critical sectors like banking, education and government at high risk of being targeted. Fine and penalties are not strictly enforced which lets cybercriminals get away with it.

I believe Nepal should adopt the following solutions to bridge the gaps:

- Sector-specific policies should be developed and implemented.
- Strictly enforce laws and take necessary actions when needed to ensure implementation of such policies.
- Make the maximum use of AI and use AI tools for detection, prevention and response of threats such as cloud solutions and optimizing machine learning algorithms.
- Provide comprehensive training and knowledge about cybersecurity, risks and how one can safeguard their assets against threat actors.

Although the listed points may not be adequate, they can pave a way for better cyber resilience in Nepal.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Research Method

In this, three A-grade commercial banks of Nepal were selected and their cybersecurity policies were compared with that of an international bank and carried out a study using case study method where data was gathered through publicly available documents, bank visits and cybersecurity frameworks documentations.

3.2 Framework Comparison and Analysis

Although there are many sector-specific cybersecurity frameworks and policies, 4 most prominent frameworks implemented worldwide are NIST, PCI DSS, SOC2 and ISO 27001. This section covers the common policies of the frameworks as well as their distinctive policies and their relation to the protection of the banking sector.

3.2.1 Common policies of Frameworks

- **Data Protection and Encryption:** All frameworks utilizes encryption methods for protection and storage of sensitive data. PCI DSS, NIST, ISO 27001 and SOC2 all advocate cryptographic methods to encrypt data and maintain customer data privacy.
- **Access Control:** All frameworks implement some form of access control policies where only authorised individuals can access the systems. Multifactor Authentication (MFA), role-based access control, and biometrics are common security measures. Such implementations help prevent fraud and internal breaches.
- **Incident Detection, Response and Recovery:** All frameworks include detecting and managing security incidents. PCI DSS emphasises on logging and monitoring whereas the NIST framework has a step-by-step procedure for detection, response and recovery. SOC2 emphasizes on business continuity and recovery. Speedy response is important in banking to mitigate damages.

- **Regulatory Compliance:** Regulatory compliance ensures adherence to security standards and legal requirements. PCI DSS enforces strict rules, while ISO 27001, NIST CSF, and SOC2 focus on audits and documentation. For banks, it builds trust, ensures legal protection, and supports operations [17].

3.2.2 Distinctive policies of Frameworks

- **PCI DSS:** PCI DSS focuses on securing card transactions and has policies such as the Payment Application Data Security Standard (PA DSS) compliance used to ensure that payment applications are secure and helps organizations protect the user's data [18].
- **ISO 27001:** ISO 27001 includes policies such as ISO/IEC 27017 for cloud security. By guaranteeing privacy and regulatory compliance, these assist banks in protecting consumer data when utilizing cloud services.
- **NIST CSF:** Regarded as the gold standard in information security, NIST Special Publication 800-53 focuses on secure digital systems such as ATMs which ensures banks implement authentication and security control and prioritizes customer privacy [19].
- **SOC2:** SOC2 has Trust Services Criteria (TSA) which is an auditing procedure that ensures availability, privacy and secured third-party integrations. This encourages trust between banks and their associates with the customers [20].
- **PSD2:** PSD2 implements the Regulatory Technical Standards (RTS) which ensures online payments security along with customer identity verifications and sharing customer data with third-party vendors securely with strong customer authentication (SCA) and API communication [21].

3.3 Case Study on Cybersecurity Policies: Nepalese vs. International Banks

In order to carry out a comprehensive and comparative analysis, A-grade commercial banks of Nepal were chosen and their cybersecurity policies were obtained and compared with those of JPMorgan Chase & Co., one of the largest and most influential banks located in New York, USA. JPMC was chosen for its global reputation and implementation of cybersecurity policies in line with global standards.

Overview of JPMC policies: JPMC implements policies that take the global standards such as NIST, PCI DSS and ISO 27001 as its basis and the policies focus on prevention as well as detection of data breaches and quick incident response.

- JPMC follows the AES-256 encryption to protect the sensitive data of the customer. Encryption methods are used in storage and communication.
- JPMC prioritizes MFA along with role based access control (RBAC). They have also implemented biometrics for the employee's authentication.
- They have 24/7 monitoring of global threats in the Security Operations Centre which has highly advanced tools and technologies with AI integration for potential breaches.
- They conduct regular cybersecurity audits on third-party vendors and are constantly providing cybersecurity training to employees regarding phishing, social engineering and other types of attacks.
- JPMC invests over \$600 million per year in cybersecurity and has over 3000 cybersecurity professionals and aligns their policies with global standards which ensures that JPMC meets regulatory and industry standards globally [22].

Comparison with Nepalese banks:

I. Encryption standards and practices:

- Nepal's banking sectors implement NRB information security aligning cybersecurity policies but they aren't up to the standards like the AES-256.
- NRB guidelines require banks to have strong cryptography and end-to-end encryption but the implementation and uniformity of E2EE varies on each bank's technological infrastructure and resources, meaning the practical application isn't consistent across all Nepalese banks.
- Additionally, CCTV must be installed at ATM locations by Nepalese banks in order to take clear images of people carrying out transactions without recording the PIN.
- Together with encryption, these security measures seek to safeguard banking's digital and physical components, although the implementation isn't consistent.

II. Authentication and access control:

- Nepalese banks have implemented MFA and biometrics for employees but they aren't multi-layered as compared to JPMC. A study by Accenture in 2022 mentions that MFA reduced unauthorized access by 99% but only 50% of south Asian banks, including Nepal, have MFA for other than employee's access.
- NRB guidelines also prioritized periodic assessments and evaluation of access controls with close supervision of people with privileged access.

III. Risk management and Vulnerability Assessment:

- Nepalese banks conduct period reviews and risk assessments and checks if CIA triad is maintained. Regular VAPT is also conducted at least twice a

year to identify vulnerabilities and develop patches. This does align with the international standards.

- However, Nepal doesn't have the technology and resources allocated to address real-time vulnerability and threat detection as compared to banks like JPMC.
- NRB guidelines also include hardening systems by configuring systems, firewalls and software as well as updating and patching systems but because of inconsistent implementation on banks, it is inadequate.

IV. Incident Response and Downtime Recovery:

- Nepalese banks aim to resume critical operations within 2 hours of downtime whereas top banks, like JPMC, according to Gartner's report, resolve 85% of threats within 15 minutes.
- Nepalese banks lack real time threat monitoring capabilities along with inadequate specializations and tools used for it.

In contrast, Nepalese commercial banks' cybersecurity policies might not be as thorough as JPMC's, particularly when it comes to putting multi-layered access control or advanced encryption techniques into practice. Since many Nepalese banks are still yet to implement international practices, they have not specialized incident response teams or real-time threat monitoring. Although Nepalese banks have strong frameworks and use technologies like SIEM, FIM, and VAPT, they still need to improve their resource allocation and practices to fully align to international standards like JPMC's.

3.4 Recommendations

Here are some recommendations Nepal can follow to align the cybersecurity practices with global standards.

- i. Implementing global frameworks:** Nepal should develop frameworks in alignment with internationally recognized cybersecurity frameworks such as

NIST, ISO 27001 and PCI DSS which will help in risk management, data protection and solving sector-specific vulnerabilities.

- ii. **Sector-specific policies:** Nepal should introduce sector-specific cybersecurity policies with major focus on banking, health and education while aligning with global standards.
- iii. **Regular VAPT:** Nepal should mandate organizations to conduct periodic Vulnerability Assessment and Penetration Testing (VAPT) using advanced tools and developing timely patches and updates.
- iv. **Strict Enforcement:** The existing laws such as the ETA and National Cybersecurity Policy 2023 should be strictly implemented with adequate resources being allocated to the cybersecurity department.
- v. **Awareness and training:** Conducting regular cybersecurity awareness and providing training to customers, employees, regardless of the hierarchy on different types of cyber-attacks such as social engineering, phishing and how they can be safe from it.
- vi. **Authentication and access control:** All organizations should implement Multi Factor Authentication (MFA), biometrics and role-based access control while regularly conducting audits to address breaches before significant damage is done.

Nepal can improve its cybersecurity resilience, protect critical sectors like banking, and align to international standards if it implements these suggestions, creating a safe and strong digital environment.

Chapter 4: Conclusion

In conclusion, the report covers the existing gaps between Nepal's cybersecurity frameworks and policies and globally implemented standards, with the banking sector being the prime focus. As digitalization is increasing rapidly, critical sectors such as banking need to have robust cybersecurity policies. Although Nepal has introduced frameworks and policies such as the ETA 2063 and National Cybersecurity Policy 2023, Nepal's cybersecurity infrastructure is yet to meet the globally recognized standards and address emerging cyber threats such as identification of threats, assessment, detection and minimizing downtime.

Globally implemented standards such as the NIST, ISO 27001, PCI DSS, SOC2 focus on sector-specific cyber security policies and provide comprehensive guidelines to tackle against cyber-attacks. The comparison between JPMorgan Chase & Co. and the Nepalese commercial banks reveals a huge difference in cybersecurity policies.

Despite having made progress in aligning the policies with global standards, they are still lacking in implementation. They lack sector-specific policies, have limited resources and the fines and penalties aren't strictly implemented. Therefore, it is crucial for Nepal to adopt global standards and policies to enclose the gaps and strengthen cybersecurity policies.

References

- [1] S. Shea, "TechTarget," TechTarget, 2 February 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/cybersecurity>. [Accessed 1 December 2024].
- [2] J. Ryerse, "connectwise," connectwise, 5 May 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.connectwise.com/blog/cybersecurity/11-best-cybersecurity-frameworks>. [Accessed 30 November 2024].
- [3] L. Gupta, "Issues of Cyber security and its solutions in Nepalese Context," *NPRC Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 122-127, 2024.
- [4] Prime Law Nepal, "primelawnepal," primelawnepal, 7 August 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://primelawnepal.com/cyber-crime-laws-in-nepal/#:~:text=In%20Nepal%2C%20the%20Nepal%20Police,to%20prevent%20cybercrime%20in%20Nepal..> [Accessed 30 November 2024].
- [5] A. Ojha, "Kathmandu post," 17 August 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://kathmandupost.com/science-technology/2023/08/17/government-s-cybersecurity-policy-raises-privacy-and-implementation-concerns>. [Accessed 30 Nov 2024].
- [6] Nepal Desk, "Nepal Desk," 13 August 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://nepaldesk.com/news/cyber-security-policy-2080>. [Accessed 2024 November 2024].
- [7] M. J. Pulami, "NIICE," NIICE, 12 April 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://niice.org.np/archives/4061>. [Accessed 1 Dec 2024].
- [8] P. Kirvan, "TechTarget," TechTarget, 27 Oct 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/tip/IT-security-frameworks-and-standards-Choosing-the-right-one>. [Accessed 1 Dec 2024].

- [9] NIST, “The NIST Cybersecurity,” NIST, 2024.
- [1 M. Soohoo, “HYPR,” HYPR, 14 Oct 2024. [Online]. Available:
0] <https://blog.hypr.com/top-financial-services-cybersecurity-regulations#:~:text=A%20Global%20Focus%20on%20Financial,strong%20authentication%20and%20cyber%20resilience..> [Accessed 1 Dec 2024].
- [11 flexi, “flexi,” flexi, 2024. [Online]. Available:
] <https://www.flexi.com/soc-2-compliance/>. [Accessed 1 Dec 2024].
- [1 D. R. Subedi, “enepalese,” enepalese, 13 july 2015. [Online]. Available:
2] <https://www.enepalese.com/2015/07/32099.html>. [Accessed 1 Dec 2024].
- [1 lawimperial, “lawimperial,” lawimperial, 2024. [Online]. Available:
3] <https://www.lawimperial.com/highlights-of-electronic-transactions-act-2006/#:~:text=What%20are%20the%20Major%20Provisions,and%20Acknowledgement%20of%20Electronic%20Records.> [Accessed 1 Dec 2024].
- [1 N. Kshetri, “Cyber Strategy of Government of Nepal (GoN,” Rochester Institute of
4] Technology, Rochester , 2017.
- [1 N. R. BANK, “Cyber Resilience Guidelines,” NEPAL RASTRA BANK, Kathmandu,
5] 2023.
- [1 L. Gupta, “NPRC Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,” *v1i2.69333122Issues of
6] Cyber security and its solutions in Nepalese Context*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 122-127, 2024.
- [1 bitsight, “bitsight,” 27 Feb 2024. [Online]. Available:
7] <https://www.bitsight.com/blog/7-cybersecurity-frameworks-to-reduce-cyber-risk>.
[Accessed 23 Dec 2024].
- [1 pcisecuritystandards, “Payment Card Industry (PCI),” pcisecuritystandards council,
8] USA, 2013.

- [1] hyperproof, “hyperproof,” hyperproof, Dec 2024. [Online]. Available:
9] <https://hyperproof.io/nist-800-53/>. [Accessed 23 Dec 2024].
- [2] barradvisory, “barradvisory,” 13 Dec 2024. [Online]. Available:
0] <https://www.barradvisory.com/resource/the-5-trust-services-criteria-explained/>.
[Accessed 23 Dec 2024].
- [2] European Central Bank, “The regulatory technical standards,” *Official Journal of the*
1] *European Union*, vol. 61, p. 68, 2018.
- [2] JPMorgan Chase & Co., “Powering Growth with Curiosity and Heart Annual Report
2] 2023,” JPMorgan Chase & Co. , USA, 2023.
- [2] C. Kothari, “Research Methodology : Methods and Techniques,” in *Research*
3] *Methodology*, Rajasthan, New Age International Publisher, 2024, p. 418.
- [2] dash, “Dash,” 2024. [Online]. Available:
4] <https://www.dashsdk.com/resource/soc-2-trust-services-criteria-tsc/>. [Accessed 23
Dec 2024].